

Rubiadin. Part II. Synthesis of 2-Methyl-1:3-dioxy-anthraquinone.

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It has been shown by one of us that rubiadin cannot be 1-methyl-2:4-dioxyanthraquinone (this *Journal*, 1927, 4, 535) and it appeared to us to be extremely probable that rubiadin has the formula 2-methyl-1:3-dioxyanthraquinone—a formula which has been rejected by Schunck and Marchlewski. (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 960). To settle this matter we decided to repeat Schunck and Marchlewski's experiment.

Schunck and Marchlewski condensed 2:6-dioxy-*p*-toluic acid with benzoic acid. In this reaction there is a considerable chance of the formation of a tetraoxy-dimethylantraquinone by the condensation of two molecules of dioxy-*p*-toluic acid.

This anthrachryson is likely to interfere with the melting point of the compound sought for. In order to minimise the chance of the formation of anthrachryson we employed a large excess of benzoic acid. In fact for every molecule of 2:6-dioxy-*p*-toluic acid ten to eleven molecules of benzoic acid were used. In this way a better yield of dioxymethylantraquinone was obtained and the

formation of anthrachryson was almost entirely prevented. The condensation product, after removing excess of benzoic acid by steam distillation, was repeatedly crystallised from benzene when 2-methyl-1:3-dioxy-anthraquinone was obtained as bright yellow crystals melting at 290° (which is the melting point of rubiadin itself). Schunck and Marchlewski describe 2-methyl-1:3-dioxyanthraquinone as orange needles melting at 282° and on quickly heating at 290°, and dissolving in sulphuric acid giving a brownish red solution. Our compound melts at 290° and gives with sulphuric acid an orange yellow solution. Rubiadin melts at 290° and gives with sulphuric acid a yellow solution. The acetyl derivative was next prepared by heating with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine. On crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 225° which is the melting point of acetyl rubiadin. Schunck and Marchlewski noted 217-218° as the melting point of their derivative. As regards solubility in different solvents (ether, alcohol, benzene, acetic acid, caustic soda, baryta water) our observations are in accord with those of Schunck and Marchlewski.

All these prove conclusively that rubiadin is 2-methyl-1:3-dioxy-anthraquinone. The discrepancies in the melting points of the mother substance and its acetyl derivative observed by Schunck and Marchlewski must have been due to the presence of impurities.

We are now engaged in the synthesis of Munjisthin another hydroxyanthraquinone derivative present in Indian madder which we have reasons to regard as an oxidation product of rubiadin.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sulphonation of p-Toluic Acid.—The sulphonation was effected by the method of Weinreich (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 982). *p*-Toluic acid (10 g.) was thoroughly mixed with phosphorous pentoxide (6-7 g.) by shaking in a well-stoppered flask and introduced quickly into a tube. Conc. sulphuric acid (6 c.c.) and 657 sulphuric acid (27 g.) were then added. The tube after being sealed was heated for 3-4 hours at 210-220°, the temperature was then gradually raised to 250° and maintained there for about an hour. After cooling the contents were poured on crushed ice and neutralised with barium carbonate and then boiled. The barium salt of the sulphonic acid occurring in the

filtrate was converted into the potassium salt by adding K_2CO_3 soln. and filtering. The potassium salt was obtained by evaporation of the filtrate.

The alkali fusion was conducted as follows:—The thoroughly powdered potassium salt, about 25 gms. being taken each time, was added in small quantities at a time to fused potash. The addition was made at about 210-220°. The temperature was then gradually raised to about 260° and maintained there until an almost clear melt was obtained. The operation lasts for about an hour and a half.

Separation of 2:6-Dioxy-p-toluic Acid.—The fused product after extraction with water and acidification was extracted with ether. After distilling off the ether, the residue was dried on a porous plate and then extracted with small quantities of toluene from which 2:6-dioxy-p-toluic acid separated on cooling, m.p. 175-176°. The residue insoluble in toluene was identified as mono-oxy-terephthalic acid.

Examination of the Residue: Hydroxyterephthalic Acid.—The residue left after extraction with toluene was repeatedly boiled with toluene in which hydroxy terephthalic acid is sparingly soluble. The mass left was next boiled with barium carbonate and filtered, when the barium salt of the acid goes into solution. This was next acidified and extracted with ether. After removing the ether by distillation, the residue was dried on a porous plate. This was next esterified in the usual manner by refluxing on the water-bath with methyl alcohol and conc. sulphuric acid. The ester was washed with sodium carbonate solution and repeatedly crystallised from methyl alcohol when it was obtained as crystals, m.p. 93°. According to Burkhardt (*Ber.*, 1887, 10, 146) the m.p. of hydroxyterephthalic acid methyl ester is 94°. (Found: C, 56.88; H, 5.19. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 57.14; H, 4.76 per cent.)

Condensation of 2:6-Dioxy-p-toluic Acid with Benzoic Acid.—2:6-Dioxy-p-toluic acid (4 g.) was mixed with benzoic acid (32 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (about 200 g.) and heated on the oil-bath at 120° for 15 hrs. The reaction product was poured on crushed ice, filtered and the mass, after removal of excess of benzoic acid by steam distillation, was recrystallised from benzene, when 1:3-dioxy-2-methylanthraquinone was obtained as crystals, m.p.

290°. These dried at 100° gave the following results on analysis. (Found. C, 70.39; H, 4.81. $C_{15}H_8O_4$ requires C, 70.86; H, 3.93 per cent.).

Acetyl Derivative of 1:3-Dioxy-2-methylantraquinone.—The dioxymethylantraquinone obtained was heated on the sand-bath with excess of acetic anhydride and one or two drops of pyridine for about six hours. The product was heated repeatedly with alcohol on the water-bath. The residue was crystallised from alcohol when the acetyl derivative was obtained as shining crystals melting at 225°.

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